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The Role of Motivation to Dance Engagement and Psychological Well-being

Joseph Lobo^{1*}, Bryan Dale Bernardo¹, Edison Buan¹, Duane Ramirez¹, Grace Ang¹,
Xennell Joshua Alfonso¹, Diana Varona¹, Jeffrey Mabaga¹, Joven Malig¹

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ABSTRACT

The positive effect of dance engagement on the psychological well-being of individuals has been consistently established based on previously conducted studies. On the other side, no evidence was found in the moderating and mediating role of motivation in the relationship between the two variables. As a solution, this study is focused on determining the moderating and mediating role of dance motivation to dance engagement and psychological well-being. This study has adopted three questionnaires, namely: Dance Motivation Questionnaire (DMQ), the Sports Engagement Scale (SPS), and Psychological Wellbeing Scale (PWS). Additionally, Partial Least-Squares Structural Equation Modelling (PLS-SEM) using Smart-PLS4 was performed to analyze the data. Analysis based on factor loading, average variance extracted (AVE), Fornell-Larcker Criterion, Cross loading, and HTMT were performed to establish the reliability and validity of the questionnaires (convergent and discriminant). After surveying 117 students taking Bachelor of Performing Arts at City College of Angeles, dance engagement positively effects students' psychological well-being, which is consistent based on previously conducted studies. On the other hand, motivation has no moderating and mediating role in the relationship between the two variables. The study highly suggests conducting a similar study to support or refute the claim of this investigation.

INTRODUCTION

Dancing is a form of artistic expression and communication which involves the movement of the body through time and space (Carey *et al.*, 2019). Moreover, it is considered an activity that involves coordinating movements with music, as well as brain activation due to its demand on learning and remembering new steps (Douka *et al.*, 2019). Medically, dancing is a popular form of physical exercise and studies have shown that dancing can decrease anxiety, increase self-esteem, and improve psychological well-being (Maraz *et al.*, 2015). The positive effect of dance on the psychological well-being of individuals has been very much established by various studies that were already conducted. Engaging in dance has been well known to provide a lot of psychological benefits (Maraz *et al.*, 2015). Moreover, it has the potential to decrease psychological distress, increase trait mindfulness, and enhance the quality of life (Laird *et al.*, 2021). On the other hand, the role of motivation in the relationship between the two variables has not yet been established, as no previous studies in the local and international settings have been found.

The researcher exhausted all available resources from various databases but to no avail. To provide new and valuable information regarding the role of motivation, a study should be conducted. This study is highly significant as it will provide evidence on the mediating and moderating role of motivation to engagement and psychological well-being. Moreover, there is a scarcity of evidence in the Philippines, most especially in the field of dance education, as dance research only occupies a limited sector in the Philippines (Lobo *et al.*, 2022a; Villaruz, n.d.).

LITERATURE REVIEW

Dance Motivation

According to Tohidi & Jabbari (2012), motivation is the driver of guidance, control, and persistence in human behavior. There have been studies that were conducted concerning the substantial role of motivation in our leisure behavior. For example, in the case of alcohol drinking, social, enhancement, and coping motives explain up to 50% of the variance in adolescent alcohol use (Schick *et al.*, 2022; Sjödin *et al.*, 2021). Additionally, motivation also plays an important role (if not determining) in the case of smoking cigarettes (Creswell & Skrzynski, 2021; Ely *et al.*, 2021), ingesting other psychoactive substances (Bhandari *et al.*, 2021; Kahsay *et al.*, 2019), gambling (Macía *et al.*, 2022; Mathieu *et al.*, 2020), online gaming (Šporčić & Glavak-Tkalić, 2018), and exercise (Rahman *et al.*, 2019; Vučković *et al.*, 2022). As bases on examining the role of motivation to dance engagement and psychological well-being, the examination of the motivational background of dancing could be arguably just as important.

Dance Engagement and Psychological Well-being

The findings of Bai *et al.* (2022) revealed that plaza dancing has a significant positive effect on psychological well-being. Mukherjee & Jaiswal (2021) have also discovered that classical dance forms enhance one's psychological well-being. Also, Tao *et al.* (2022), showed that dancing provides physiological and psychological benefits to healthy and medically compromised populations. Analogous to the result findings of Douse *et al.* (2020), intergenerational dance and art projects can have wide-reaching positive impacts on both social and psychological well-being. Additionally, Hrusova's (2015)

¹ Physical Education Department, City College of Angeles, Angeles City, Pampanga, Philippines

* Corresponding author's e-mail: jtoledolobo@gmail.com

findings discovered that dancing positively influences psychological state. Similar to the findings of Cardas (2015) constant practice of dance movement has a positive effect on psychological well-being. As mentioned earlier, previously conducted studies have established the positive effect of dance engagement on psychological well-being. Hence, this can be hypothesized as follows:

H1: Dance engagement has a positive effect on psychological well-being.

The Mediating and moderating role of dance motivation to dance engagement and psychological well-being

Rehman *et al.* (2020) found that social support and learning motivation significantly indicated the link between burnout and psychological well-being. Moreover, Hussain *et al.* (2020) found that intrinsic motivation positively and significantly mediates the relationship between abusive supervision and psychological well-being. On the other hand, Bányai *et al.* (2019) findings revealed that no difference was observed between the mediating effect of motivations to psychiatric distress and gaming disorder. The findings mentioned earlier are related to the mediating role of motivation to other variables concerning psychological well-being. After numerous attempts to search for related studies in relationship with dance engagement and psychological well-being and the mediating effect of dance motivation, unfortunately, no previous investigations were conducted. Based on

the review of the literature performed, hence, it can be hypothesized that:

H2: Dance motivation positively/negatively mediates the relationship between dance engagement and psychological well-being.

Most of the research papers that were found chiefly concern the impact of motivation on the psychological well-being of individuals and vice-versa. Such as from the study of González Olivares *et al.* (2020) found a positive correlation between perceived psychological well-being and the motivation of students toward the beginning of university studies. Additionally, intrinsic motivation positively affects the psychological well-being of nurses in Indonesia (Pardede, 2018). found a significant correlation between psychological well-being and work motivation among staff nurses in government hospitals in Port Said. Lastly, the study by Kaur (2013) revealed that psychological well-being plays an imperative role in motivation. As mentioned earlier, these studies correlate the relationship and determine the effect of motivation on psychological well-being (vice-versa) from different populations and disciplines.

On the other hand, no studies were found concerning the moderating role of motivation in the relationship between dance engagement and psychological well-being. In relation to this, the study will test the following hypothesis:

H3: Dance motivation does not moderate the relationship between dance engagement and psychological well-being.

Figure 1: Conceptual Framework

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Participants, Sampling Technique and Sample Size

The participants of the study are students who are currently taking the degree Bachelor of Performing Arts enrolled this Academic year 2022-2023 at City College of Angeles, located in the City of Angeles, Philippines. The respondents for the study were identified by using the Purposive sampling technique. This sampling technique is a non-probability procedure where the researcher deliberately chooses participants for the study due to the qualities the participants possess (Lobo *et al.*, 2022b; Rodriguito *et al.*, 2022). The total number of respondents is 117 accepted for data analysis after performing data cleaning.

Instruments

An online survey questionnaire was sent to all respondents. Three different questionnaires were adapted and utilized for this study. First, the Dance Motivation Questionnaire (DMQ) by Hancox *et al.* (2015). It is a 24-item questionnaire which aims to assess the level of motivation of students for dancing or performing. Second, the Sport Engagement Scale (SES) by Guillén & Martínez-Alvarado (2014). SES is a 15-item questionnaire which aims the level of engagement of respondents in sports. For this specific questionnaire, some words were altered such as changing sports into dance to tailor-fit the questions to the scope of this current investigation. Lastly, the Psychological Wellbeing Scale (PWS) by Ryff

& Keyes (1995). It is a shortened questionnaire (18-item) from the original 42-item questionnaire. PWS aims to determine the level of the overall psychological wellbeing.

Data Analysis

The Partial Least Squares-Structural Equation Modelling (PLS-SEM) using SmartPLS 4 was utilized for the statistical analysis. Concerning the measurement model, Hair *et al.* (2021) suggested that the outer loadings of each item and the average variance extracted (AVE) should be considered in establishing convergent validity. Additionally, Hair *et al.* also advised that the Fornell-Larcker criterion and cross-loading should be performed to establish discriminant validity. The Heterotrait-Monotrait (HTMT) criterion was also suggested as another analysis in assessing discriminant validity. In line with all of these, the forementioned criteria will all be applied in order to assess the measurement and structural models.

Ethical Considerations

The respondents were informed about the study’s

objectives, the instruments, and the constructs that will be measured. Additionally, the researcher has provided the benefits of the study for the college and the scientific community. The respondents were required to provide their consent by clicking the agreement attached in the Google forms. They were also given the freedom to decide whether to participate or decline. Participants were also informed that there might be minor risks in their participation in the study, such as the feeling of being uncomfortable in answering personal and sensitive survey questions. Likewise, they were told that no monetary compensation would be provided for giving information. Given these circumstances, participants were free to withdraw or to ask for a debriefing of the study anytime.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Figure 2 illustrates the demographic profile of the Bachelor of Performing Arts Program students based on gender. Most of the respondents who answered the online survey are male (n=113), which corresponds to 63.8% of the total population, followed by the female (n=35) 19.8% and prefer not to say (n=29) 16.4%

Figure 2: Demographic Profile

Table 1: Measurement Model Results

Constructs	Items	Loadings	Cronbach's Alpha	Composite Reliability	Average Variance Extracted
Dance Engagement	ENG3	0.791	0.943	0.989	0.675
	ENG5	0.877			
	ENG6	0.782			
	ENG8	0.745			
	ENG9	0.715			
	ENG11	0.773			
	ENG12	0.885			
	ENG14	0.928			
Dance Motivation	MOV3	0.738	0.946	0.964	0.649
	MOV7	0.790			
	MOV8	0.759			
	MOV12	0.849			
	MOV14	0.711			

	MOV16	0.821			
	MOV17	0.851			
	MOV18	0.797			
	MOV19	0.884			
	MOV20	0.870			
	MOV22	0.770			
Psychological Wellbeing	PSY4	0.853	0.933	0.934	0.834
	PSY5	0.973			
	PSY6	0.919			
	PSY16	0.905			

respectively. In order to measure the reliability of each item, a factor loading should be performed. A threshold value of equal to or greater than 0.7 for each item's loading is considered reliable (Hair *et al.*, 2021). The Cronbach's Alpha value and composite reliability should be equal to or greater than 0.7. As illustrated in Table 1, all items are reliable and satisfactorily complied with the criteria except for ENG1, ENG2, ENG4, ENG7, ENG10, and ENG13 for the Dance Engagement (SES); MOV1, MOV2, MOV4, MOV5, MOV6, MOV9, MOV10, MOV11, MOV13, MOV15, MOV21, MOV 23, and MOV24 for the Dance Motivation Questionnaire (DMQ); and, PSY1, PSY2, PSY3, PSY7, PSY8, PSY9, PSY10, PSY11, PSY12, PSY13, PSY14, PSY15, PSY17, and PSY17 for the Psychological Wellbeing Scale (PWS) since their factor loadings are below the threshold of 0.7. Therefore, these items were removed from the structure. On the one hand, the Average Variance Extracted (AVE)

is used to validate constructs (dos Santos & Cirillo, 2021). In order to determine the convergent validity, AVE should be equal or higher than 0.5, and the corresponding p-value should be at most 0.5 (Fauzi *et al.*, 2021; Hair *et al.*, 2021; Lacap & Alfonso, 2022). As shown in Table 1, the Cronbach's Alpha and the composite reliability values are more significant than 0.7, and the AVE are greater than 0.5. Hence, convergent validity has been established. In order to establish the discriminant validity, the Fornell-Larcker criterion, cross loadings, and HTMT should be inspected. Regarding Fornell-Larcker criterion, the square root of AVE (diagonal value) in each variable should exceed the correlation of latent variables, as presented in Table 3. Additionally, the cross loading of each indicator should be higher than the loadings of its corresponding variables' indicators, which is shown in Table 4. Lastly, the HTMT value should be less than 0.85 which is illustrated in Table 5.

Table 2: Fornell-Larcker Criterion

Dance Engagement		Dance Motivation	Psychological Wellbeing	Motivation x Engagement
Dance Engagement	0.822			
Dance Motivation	-0.050	0.805		
Psychological Wellbeing	0.533	-0.151	0.913	
Motivation x Engagement	0.463	-0.074	0.175	

Table 3: Cross Loading Results

Dance Engagement		Dance Motivation	Psychological Wellbeing	Motivation x Engagement
ENG3	0.791	0.123	0.318	0.329
ENG5	0.877	-0.089	0.320	0.477
ENG6	0.782	-0.055	0.128	0.528
ENG8	0.745	0.043	0.254	0.390
ENG9	0.715	-0.032	0.156	0.390
ENG11	0.773	-0.023	0.582	0.194
ENG12	0.885	-0.100	0.375	0.471
ENG14	0.928	-0.091	0.604	0.460
ENG15	0.874	-0.070	0.571	0.405
MOV3	-0.010	0.738	-0.151	-0.058
MOV7	-0.051	0.790	-0.100	-0.050
MOV8	-0.021	0.759	-0.055	-0.079

MOV12	-0.065	0.849	-0.168	-0.036
MOV14	-0.020	0.711	-0.071	-0.116
MOV16	-0.062	0.821	-0.055	-0.076
MOV17	-0.022	0.851	-0.141	-0.054
MOV18	-0.019	0.797	-0.109	-0.093
MOV19	-0.012	0.884	-0.157	-0.044
MOV20	-0.057	0.870	-0.103	-0.066
MOV22	-0.099	0.770	-0.111	-0.047
PSY4	0.471	-0.192	0.853	0.204
PSY5	0.501	-0.163	0.973	0.169
PSY6	0.449	-0.031	0.919	0.030
PSY16	0.517	-0.148	0.905	0.214
Motivation x Engagement	0.463	-0.074	0.175	1.000

Table 4: Heterotrait-Monotrait (HTMT) Criterion

Dance Engagement		Dance Motivation	Psychological Wellbeing	Motivation x Engagement
Dance Engagement				
Dance Motivation	0.097			
Psychological Wellbeing	0.471	0.150		
Motivation x Engagement	0.503	0.083	0.175	

Figure 3: Structure Model

Table 5: Hypotheses test results

Hypothesis	Path	Path Coefficient	p-value	Decision
H1	ENG → PSY	0.573	0.000	Supported
H2	ENG X MOV → PSY	-0.067	0.469	Rejected
H3	ENG → MOV → PSY	0.006	0.761	Supported

Based on the results, Figure 3 and Table 4 illustrates moderating and mediating effect of motivation to engagement and psychological well-being. The findings revealed that dance engagement has a positive effect to the psychological wellbeing of students ($\beta = 0.57$, $p < 0.1$) which supported H1. It can be interpreted that the more students engaged in dance, it positively affects their psychological wellbeing. The findings of this investigation are similar to the discoveries of previously conducted studies (Bai *et al.*, 2022; Cardaş, 2015; Douse *et al.*, 2020; Hrusova, 2015; Tao *et al.*, 2022).

On the other hand, it was found that dance motivation does not mediate H2 ($\beta = 0.006$, $p = 0.77$) and moderate H3 ($\beta = -0.067$, $p = 0.47$) the relationship between dance engagement and psychological well-being of the students. Hence, the proposed hypotheses for the study were rejected and supported consecutively. This can be interpreted that regardless of the level of dance motivation the students have, either high or low, engaging in dance is still proven to provide positive benefits to their psychological wellbeing. Since there are no previously conducted studies concerning the role of dance

motivation to dance engagement and psychological well-being, a deeper inquiry regarding its role is warranted.

CONCLUSIONS

Based on the findings, the result on the effect of dance engagement to psychological well-being has been consistently proven to be positive. It can be construed that continuous dance participation may lead to a healthy psychological state. As dance has been demonstrated to be an effective activity that positively affects psychological well-being and even other dimensions. In relation to this, the administration of the school shall consider designing dance programs encouraging students to participate. This will serve as an intervention for the students, most especially for students who are experiencing psychological issues and to disseminate mental health awareness through dance.

Since there was no moderating and mediating effect observed regarding the role of motivation to engagement and psychological well-being, conducting a similar study to other set of population is warranted. This will confirm if the result of this study can be supported or refuted. Moreover, this study highly suggests to incorporate other variables that can mediate or moderate the relationship between the two. Exploring other factors that greatly affects the relationship between the two may provide meaningful insight that will help schools and administrators to design appropriate dance programs for students.

Lastly, the limitation of this study is that it only focuses on students who are taking Bachelor of Performing Arts. This does not generalize the entire students where this study has been conducted. Moreover, the result of this study may not be applicable to other Higher Education Institutions. Future researchers may find curiosity to conduct the same study to other set of population and compare the results from various HEIs. Above all, this study contributes new data in the body of knowledge regarding the mediating and moderating role of motivation in the relationship between dance engagement and psychological well-being.

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